

Varying Finite Elements

In Atmospheric , Hydrological or any earth science finite element calculations it has been observed at SIU that unlike man made object natural objects requires a varying number of finite elements. The Finite element density should be very high at some places , while the finite element density should be very low at some places in natural dynamics calculations in x,y,z,t. The method Varying Finite Elements is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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The physical measurement system will influence during their development and assessment. This stage will provide information regarding their potential **design risks** technical data and physical space constraints within the...

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